

Management of Squamous Cell Carcinoma of Maxilla & Maxillary Sinus: An Overview of Existing Literature

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Abstract

Historically treatment of squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) of maxilla and maxillary sinus involved surgical resection followed by radiation therapy for advanced tumors. Concurrent chemoradiation therapies have shown equal survival to surgical resection with better preservation of function. However, concurrent therapy does entail significant morbidity, and recent advances have been used to minimize that morbidity. Newer tumor specific medical therapies are anticipated to be less toxic while maintaining a high degree of efficacy. For resectable cancer, transoral laser microsurgery is a new trend in surgery for complete resection of tumors with preservation of function. Advanced reconstructive techniques that allow free transfer of soft tissue and bone from all over the body improve the functional and aesthetic outcomes following major ablative surgery. With successful surgical reconstruction, dental and prosthetic rehabilitation choices are enhanced. With these newer therapies and methods of reconstruction, each patient needs to be carefully evaluated to maximize the possibility of cure and level of function, and minimize the morbidity associated with treatment. Combined chemotherapy and radiation protocols are associated with increased acute and chronic toxicities that may affect the quality of life due to the impact upon oral disease and oral function. Healthcare providers must be aware of advances in cancer management and its implications in patients' overall well being to effectively care for them.

Keywords: malignancy, maxillary squamous cell carcinoma, recurrence, sinus tumour, surgery, therapy

Introduction

Oral Squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) is the most common type and represents more than 90% of all malignant tumors.¹ More than 640,000 new cases are reported worldwide annually,² with high rate of morbidity and mortality of >50%. In 2023, OSCC resulted in 135,000 deaths in India, up from 84,000 deaths in 2020.⁴ The reason for such high prevalence of OSCC in India is primarily tobacco consumed in form of gutka, snuff, betel quid,⁵ and mishri. Areca nut is used by ~200–400 million people, particularly Indo-Asians and Chinese,⁶ and is also a risk factor for maxillary squamous cell carcinoma and sinus tumor.⁷ Chronic exposure to potential carcinogens like tobacco and alcohol damages the mucosal lining of the oral cavity, increasing the risk of developing squamous cell carcinomas.⁸ Tobacco as a carcinogen is responsible for 90% of maxillary squamous cell carcinoma and sinus tumor cases globally.⁹ Cigarette smokers show 4–7 times higher incidences of OSCC than nonsmokers, and when alcohol or chewing tobacco is combined with cigarette smoke, the occurrence of this disease is increased by 19- to 123-folds.¹⁰

Reviewing the GLOBOCAN database

provides a worldwide picture of the incidences of OSCC. In 2022, there were an estimated 300,000 new cases of lip/oral cavity cancer worldwide, corresponding to 2.1% of all cancer cases (with age standardized rate of world population [ASR] of 4.0 per 100,000). Among these cases, 199,000 cases occurred in men and 101,000 cases in women. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) ASR for lip/oral cavity cancer is highest (6.4 per 100,000) for the Southeast Asian region, followed by the European region (4.6 per 100,000), the Eastern Mediterranean region (4.6 per 100,000), the Americas region (4.1 per 100,000), the Africa region (2.7 per 100,000) and the Western Pacific region (2.0 per 100,000). Worldwide mortality estimations for lip/oral cavity cancer for 2012 includes an ASR of 2.7 per 100,000.¹¹ Epidemiological studies carried out in Australia, Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Germany, Netherlands, Slovenia, Slovakia, and Ukraine have reported decreasing or

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stabilized trends in the occurrence of OSCC. The reason for this decreased or stabilized trend is decreased use of tobacco and alcohol in these regions. However, countries like Finland, Iceland, and Ireland have exhibited markedly increasing trends in the incidence despite declining use of tobacco and alcohol. This increase in OSCC can be explained by involvement of other etiological factors such as human papillomavirus and unprotected oral sex.

Goal Therapy

Approximately one-third of all tumors in patients with squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) of the maxilla and maxillary sinus (M/MS) present as stage I/II disease. Treatment consists of local/regional therapy involving either radiation therapy (RT), surgery or a combination of modalities.¹² The prognosis for these patients is excellent with expected cure rates of 80% and 65% for stage I and stage II disease, respectively.¹³

Approximately two-thirds of patients present with stage III or IV disease.¹⁴ The prognosis for these patients is worse than the prognosis for locally confined disease, with 5-year survival rates of only 10–40% and cure rates of 30%.¹⁵ Most patients die secondary to locoregional persistent or recurrent disease. In addition, treatment related morbidity can be severe due to acute and chronic sequelae such as mucositis, xerostomia, dysphagia, loss of function, trismus and deformities.¹⁶ The goals of therapy in the treatment of locally advanced SCC of M/MS are cure, organ preservation, attenuation of the morbidities associated with therapy and improvement in quality of life. For those patients who achieve cure, second primary cancers pose a significant risk; therefore, prevention of second malignancies are goals of therapy in the treatment of patients with SCC of M/MS.

Approximately 5% of patients may have metastatic disease at presentation and distant metastases may subsequently develop in one-third of all patients with head and neck malignancy.^{14,16} Untreated, patients with metastatic disease have a median survival of about 4 months.¹⁷ Patients with advanced and metastatic SCC of M/MS often suffer from significant comorbidities secondary to advanced age and complications of alcohol and tobacco abuse. Those who develop metastatic disease are often heavily pretreated resulting in significant morbidity further complicating treatment.¹⁸ Palliation of symptoms and prolongation of life using chemo-therapeutic agents are the goals of therapy in patients with metastatic SCC of M/MS.

Current Practice

RT and surgery have historically comprised the core of therapy for SCC of M/MS; however, as with the treatment of most malignancies, there has been a shift towards increased use of concurrent chemotherapy for radio-sensitization and a decreased rate of distant metastases.¹⁹ For most early stages maxillary squamous cell carcinomas high cure rates are achieved with either definitive irradiation or surgery. Management decisions are largely influenced by the patient's general health, disease site, and anticipated functional and cosmetic outcome, as well as the anticipated quality of life during and following treatment.²⁰ The majority of T1 and T2 tumors of the oral tongue and oral cavity are treated with initial surgical resection because speech and swallowing function can be preserved and definitive radiation therapy

leads to a high rate of osteoradionecrosis.²¹

Osteoradionecrosis is a particular problem in tumors close to the mandible. In cases where surgical resection would result in significant dysfunction or cases in which the patient is medically inoperable, definitive irradiation can be used in an effort to preserve function with equivalent disease control.²¹

In other head and neck sites, including the larynx, oropharynx, and hypopharynx, primary surgical resection often results in significant voice and swallowing impairment, therefore; definitive radiotherapy is the preferred initial treatment.²⁰⁻²² However, the recent introduction of transoral laser microsurgery allows for resection of laryngeal, hypopharyngeal and oropharyngeal tumors with good preservation of function. This type of surgery has been popularised by Wolfgang Steiner in Germany and is being adopted by a few practitioners in the United States. Unfortunately, transoral laser microsurgery surgery is time consuming, technically demanding, and requires a larger number of new instruments. Reported cure rates are comparable to historical cure rates.²³ Large trials assessing survival and functional outcome are needed to define the role of transoral laser microsurgery in the future.

Locally advanced, resectable SCC of M/MS is treated with multimodality therapy consisting of either surgery followed by post-operative chemoradiation or chemoradiation with surgical salvage if needed. The selection of initial therapy depends on the site involved. Oral cavity lesions are often accessible for surgical therapy and radiation to the oral cavity results in high rates of complications. Initial surgical treatment allows postoperative radiation to the locoregional area at lower RT dose, and thus, a lower rate of complication associated with radiation therapy. Consequently, initial surgical resection followed by RT or chemoradiation therapy is commonly selected for resectable oral cavity tumors.²⁴

Neck Dissection

The patient populations who may benefit from a post-chemoradiation neck dissection is controversial. The decision to proceed to a post-chemoradiation neck dissection is usually dependent on both the response of nodal metastasis to therapy and initial nodal stage. Often the tumor at primary site will regress while nodal metastases remain palpable or evident on CT, necessitating postoperative neck dissection to treat the disease and to assess refractory disease.²⁵

Depending on the initial extent of nodal metastasis, up to 39% of patients who have complete clinical response will have microscopic disease in the neck dissection specimen; however, controversy remains concerning the viability of these cells.²⁶ Some centres will conduct neck dissection in patients with initial nodal staging or higher regardless of response, while others reserve neck dissection for initial N3 disease or partial response to chemoradiotherapy. The decision is often based upon the individual experiences of each institution.²⁴ More studies are required to provide evidenced based guidelines. Also, the extent of neck dissection after chemoradiation remains controversial, with some advocating radical neck dissection while others advocate selective neck dissection of levels initially involved.²⁵

Flap Reconstruction

Advances in head and neck reconstruction have improved the functional abilities and cosmetic appearance of patients

following larger and larger surgical resections. The pectoralis myocutaneous flap, first described by Ariayan in 1979, is still the workhorse for head and neck reconstruction. This is a pedicled flap that receives its blood supply from the pectoral branch of the thoraco-acromial artery, and has proven to be reliable and versatile.^{24,25} The limitations of this flap include: size of the skin paddle over the pectoralis muscle, bulk of the pectoralis muscle, pliability due to thickness of the flap, distance of reconstructive site due to reliance on the vascular pedicle, and lack of bone for maxillary reconstruction. Many other pedicled flaps have been used in head and neck reconstruction, but they all have similar limitations.²⁶

Free flap reconstruction has revolutionized both the surgical resection of SCC of M/MS and the reconstruction. The term free flap refers to the isolation of the flap on a supporting vascular supply with transfer to a new location in the body, and revascularization of the flap at the new location using microvascular techniques.²⁷ By completely freeing the flap from its vascular pedicle, the distance to the reconstructive site no longer limits the reconstruction. Flaps can be taken from all over the body and allow transfer of fascia, skin, fat, bowel, muscle and bone. With a greater number of tissues to choose from, reconstruction can be tailored to improve ultimate the cosmetic and functional outcome. The tissue composition of the flap can be chosen to match the composition of the resected tissues rather than just using any tissue that can reach the resection site.²⁸

Approaches for the management of SCC of M/MS

The mode of treatment of SCC of M/MS depends on various factors such as stage of the disease, site of the disease, and overall health status of the patient. For stage 1 and stage 2 patients with SCC of M/MS, a single line therapy by radiotherapy or surgery is the preferred initial treatment. Before 1980, surgery and/or radiation therapy was the first line of treatment for the patients of patients with advanced stage 3 and 4 cancer. However, these traditional modalities gave poor results. Thus, to improve treatment efficacy, increase local control, and increase the survival rate, systemic chemotherapy was introduced in the mid-1970s as a part of combined treatment.²⁹

Combined therapeutic and prophylactic treatment have always been used for better control of SCC of M/MS. Also, complimentary therapy as a follow-up to preventive measures has been shown to improve the management of the disease. The present review covers novel and current approaches for the treatment and management of SCC of M/MS and outlines treatments and formulation approaches such as targeted site-specific nanotechnology-based formulation for the effective treatment of this disease.

A. Surgical Intervention

Surgical removal of the tumor is done if the tumor is small enough and if surgery is likely to result in functionally satisfactory results. Chemoradiotherapy is often used with surgery, especially when a tumor is inoperable.^{25,26} After the surgery, most patients with SCC of M/MS depend on a nasogastric tube for their nutrition. Many patients are disfigured and suffer from long-term effects including fatigue, speech problems, swallowing difficulties, weakness, dizziness, hearing loss, and sinus damage. Surgery types include – maxillectomy - Medial Maxillectomy (Fig 1a), Infrastructure

Maxillectomy (Fig 1b), Suprastructure Maxillectomy (Fig 1c), Subtotal Maxillectomy (Fig 1d), Total Maxillectomy (Fig 1e), with neck-dissection. Additional reconstructive surgery such as skin graft, local flap, free flap, or a prosthetic obturator may be required to rebuild the structures removed during the excision of cancer. In general, reconstruction involves permanent closure of the opening between the mouth, sinus, and nasal cavities above. There are numerous options on how best to do that using a variety of techniques. In technical terms, a prosthetic restoration is not an actual reconstruction of the defect, as there remains an opening in the palate that is only closed with the prosthetic obturator.

Fig 1: Types of Maxillectomy

B. Chemoradiotherapy

The first line of treatment of metastatic SCC of M/MS is chemotherapy using drugs like cisplatin, carboplatin, 5-fluorouracil, docetaxel, paclitaxel and methotrexate. Chemotherapy is effective in oral carcinoma when used in combination with other treatment modalities, especially with radiation therapy. Chemotherapy and radiotherapy, when used simultaneously, gives synergistic benefit against SCC of M/MS. Also, this approach is associated with a high level of response in inoperable stages of the disease. By achieving locoregional control without surgical resection of anatomical structures, chemoradiotherapy is effective as an organ sparing approach. Along with potential delivery of active agents it uses the tumor radiosensitizing property of the agent. Also, the ionization radiation deposits energy that injures or destroys cells in the area being treated by damaging the genetic material (DNA). However, both therapies face a major drawback of nonspecific cell death resulting in mucositis, myelosuppression, and alopecia as major side effects.³⁰

C. EGFR Inhibitors Epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR)

It is a membrane-bound receptor associated with various cellular activities such as proliferation, differentiation, cell survival, and death. It activates multiple downstream cell-signaling pathways including the RAS/RAF/MEK/ERK pathway. Overactivation of this pathway is considered a factor in cancer development, metastasis, and resistant to chemotherapy.^{30,31} Maxillary squamous cell carcinoma and sinus tumor results from multiple genetic mutations that involve overexpression of EGFR, which alters the pattern of transcription and translation. EGFR, a tyrosine kinase receptor, is associated with worse prognosis in patients with OSCC.^{32,33} EGFR inhibitors alone or in combination with chemoradiotherapy have proven effective against OSCC in clinical trials.³⁴ EGFR inhibitors like nimotuzumab^{35,36} and cetuximab³⁷ exhibit antiangiogenic properties by inhibiting migration and invasion of maxillary squamous cell carcinoma and sinus tumor cells; they also significantly lower the tube formation of endothelial cells. Cetuximab is a monoclonal antibody approved as a drug for targeting EGFR and remains as the sole targeted therapy for SCC of M/MS. It is used in combination with radiation therapy in patients with untreated

locally advanced HNSCC and as monotherapy for patients with metastatic (stage 4) HSNCC.

Erlotinib has been approved for the treatment of lung cancer; however, results from a 12-month randomized chemoprevention trial evaluating the chemopreventive effect of erlotinib in patients with high-risk oral premalignant lesions by William et al. (2015) showed that erlotinib failed to improve maxillary squamous cell carcinoma and sinus tumor-free survival (CFS) versus placebo.³⁸ However, a major constraint in using these agents is the development of acquired resistance in patients who initially respond to EGFR therapy. COX-2, another molecular target in head and neck squamous cell carcinoma, can also be targeted with EGFR inhibitors, giving synergistic effect on human cancer cell lines by inducing apoptosis and decreasing the formation of the endothelium.

Pretreatment of SCC of M/MS with epidermal growth factor (EGF) increases its sensitivity; thus, EGFR expression and its signalling pathway play an important role in determining sensitivity to chemotherapeutic agents or irradiation.³⁹ Hiraishi et al. (2008) carried out studies using OSCC cell lines to investigate whether EGFR inhibitor improves cisplatin sensitivity of the OSCC. They evaluated the effect of a combination of AG 1478 (EGFR inhibitor) with cisplatin on cultured OSCC cell lines and cisplatin-resistant sublines. Their results suggest that inhibition of EGFR enhances cisplatin sensitivity of OSCC cell lines. Nimotuzumab in combination with PDT (photodynamic therapy) increased the antitumor effect of PDT in an oral tumor model; this study was carried out by Bhuvaneshwari et al. in 2015 in maxillary squamous cell carcinoma and sinus tumor cell lines and an OSCC xenografted tumor model. The combination resulted in downregulation of EGFR, Ki-67, and CD-31. In vivo cytotoxicity studies showed no toxicity on liver and kidney. Other studies have also shown that nimotuzumab and cetuximab exhibit antiangiogenic properties by inhibiting the migration and invasion of maxillary squamous cell carcinoma and sinus tumor cell lines. Chlorin e6-PDT, in combination with nimotuzumab and cetuximab, reduced cell proliferation in different maxillary squamous cell carcinoma and sinus tumor and endothelial cells.⁴⁰

D. COX-2 Inhibitors

Cyclooxygenases (COX) are rate-limiting enzymes that act as catalysts in the synthesis of prostaglandins from arachidonic acid. COX-1 and COX-2 are two isoforms of COX from which COX-2 is an inducible enzyme that is elevated during inflammation and in various cancerous tissues, including those of OSCC AND SINUS TUMOR. COX-2 is induced by carcinogens, growth factors, mitogens, cytokines, tumor promoting phorbol esters.⁴⁰ In OSCC AND SINUS TUMOR, mean levels of COX-2 mRNA are increased by 150-fold compared with normal mucosa. Overexpression of COX-2 inhibits apoptosis and immune surveillance, promotes angiogenesis, and increases metastasis; hence, COX-2 is considered an important target in the treatment of the OSCC AND SINUS TUMOR. Antimetastatic effects of certain COX-2 inhibitors suggest that these molecules have critical utility in the management of maxillary squamous cell carcinoma and sinus tumors. In vivo studies have proven that selective COX-2 inhibition suppresses tumor cell growth. Studies in animal models show that COX-2 inhibition can prevent carcinogenesis. The combined use of chemoradiotherapy with a COX-2-targeted approach has

proven effective due to its synergistic effect. Shiotani et al. (2001) and Yamamoto et al. (2013) studied the effect of nimesulide on Fisher 344 rats with induced squamous cell carcinomas of tongue.⁴⁰

These agents decreased the incidence of tongue lesions. The chemo-preventive effect of nimesulide has also been reported. COX-2 inhibitory effect of JTE-22 on mice xenografted with human KB cancer cells show that JTE-22 inhibits angiogenesis and telomerase activity, along with the cell cycle.100 Mohammad et al. (2011) studied 44 patients with SCC to determine the potential of COX-2 as a diagnostic and prognostic index of OSCC AND SINUS TUMOR. Their results suggest that COX-2-overexpressed patients were more resistant to chemoradiotherapy than under-expressed patients. Hence, COX-2 expression can be used as a prognostic marker in OSCC AND SINUS TUMOR. Minter et al. (2003) investigated the inhibitory effect of NS398 on COX-2. Their results showed that it had the potential to inhibit proliferation of oral carcinoma cell lines via mechanisms dependent on and independent of reduced prostaglandin E2 synthesis.

E. Photodynamic Therapy

Photodynamic therapy is a new approach being studied for the management of OSCC AND SINUS TUMOR. The results from several small clinical studies have shown that this therapy is effective in treating epithelial premalignant lesions and superficial carcinomas. Hematoporphyrin derivatives and its conjugates 103 or 5-ALA 104 are administered either topically or by intravenous route. These agents act as photosensitizing agents and specifically target cancerous cells. The activation of these photosensitizers occurs when the targeted tissue is exposed to a specific wavelength of light. The activated photosensitizer then transfers its energy to molecular oxygen, which causes tissue damage by generating reactive oxygen species. Although the therapy is associated with cutaneous photosensitivity as its major side effect, newer photosensitizing agents like 5-ALA show reduced occurrence of this complication. Bhuvaneshwari et al. (2015) evaluated the efficacy of chlorin-e6 photodynamic therapy in combination with an EGFR inhibitor nimotuzumab in maxillary squamous cell carcinoma and sinus tumor cell lines and an OSCC AND SINUS TUMOR xenografted tumor model. The results of this combined therapy showed reduced cell proliferation, downregulation of EGFR, ki-67, and CD31, and synergistically delayed tumor growth compared with control and PDT-treated tumors.

F. Chemoprevention

Chemoprevention of cancer is gaining significant importance in the field of cancer treatment. It is an approach that uses natural, synthetic, or biological agents for reversing, suppressing, or preventing carcinogenic progression in normal and high-risk populations.⁴¹ The success of breast cancer chemoprevention trials using tamoxifen has set standards for chemoprevention for other types of cancers. Chemo-preventive clinical trials in maxillary squamous cell carcinoma patients using isotretinoin, vitamin A, N-[4-hydroxyphenyl] retinamide, and a combination of interferon- α , α -tocopherol, and isotretinoin have shown positive results in cancer chemoprevention. Naturally occurring agents have always been appreciated for their medicinal value for both their chemo-preventive and therapeutic effects against cancer. Compounds like aspirin, folic acid, calcium, quercetin,

resveratrol, epigallocatechin-3-gallate are studied for their chemo-preventive effects. A number of polyphenols of herbal origin have been explored for the management of oral and head and neck carcinomas. Phytoconstituents with high antioxidant activities such as quercetin, resveratrol, curcumin, green tea polyphenols, ginko biloba and ellagic acid have been studied extensively for the treatment of OSCC AND SINUS TUMOR, colon cancer, and various other types of cancer. There is a need for combination therapy when one drug presents a chemo-preventive effect and another drug curtails the side effects of chemotherapy and aids in a similar line of treatment. In SCC, mucositis is a major side effect of chemotherapy and radiotherapy and is a major cause of discomfort to the patient. Combination approach provide increased efficacy with minimized toxicity. Studies have demonstrated that vitamin D and calcium combinations exert an additive effect, indicating that these two agents work together. Recently, the term "nano chemoprevention" has been coined to describe the novel approach of using nanotechnology-based formulation of chemo-preventive agents for the management of various types of cancers.

G. Nanocarrier-Based Drug Delivery Technology

Dealing with cancer is a challenge because nonselective destruction by the therapeutic agents leads impairment of vital organs. Currently, though conventional treatments of chemotherapy and radiotherapy are widely accepted for the treatment and/or management of OSCC AND SINUS TUMOR.

The benefits of these therapies must be balanced with a safety margin. The field of nanotechnology holds solutions to the limitations of the aforementioned therapies. This field is explored widely for delivery of anticancer agents and also for targeting the tumor. Various efficacious nanotechnology-based carrier systems are being widely investigated for their potential to deliver anticancer agents specifically to cancerous cells: polymeric nanoparticles, polymeric micelles, nano-emulsions and layered nano-emulsions, nano-lipomes, solid lipid nanoparticles and nano-lipid carriers, cyclo-dextrin complexes, hydrogels, metallic nanoparticles, nanocarbon tubes, and receptor-mediated drug delivery systems, among others. Although these structures are very small in comparison to the cell, they are large enough to attach multiple functional moieties to the cell surface, modifying the cell surface properties and distribution patterns.

Nanoparticles, apart from reducing the side effects of the drug agents, also improve the treatment modality by controlling their targeted delivery, facilitating constant and uniform amounts of drug at the site of the cancer lesion in the oral cavity. The increased concentration at the site facilitates penetration of the drug into the tumor. Conventional chemotherapy faces a major problem, the development of drug resistance, shortly after initial treatment reduces the efficacy of both conventional therapeutic agents and targeted therapeutic agents. This drawback can be overcome by adopting a nano-therapeutic approach. There has been very little research pertaining to targeted drug delivery to buccal mucosa for the site-specific treatment of OSCC AND SINUS TUMOR. Thus, it is very important to highlight this less explored area so that potential researchers can contribute to the development of these nano-systems.

H. Induction Chemotherapy

Induction chemotherapy is administered before surgery or radiation therapy, with a goal to improve disease control through delivery of chemotherapeutic agents to tumor cells whose vasculature has not been altered by surgery or radiotherapy.⁴⁵ To date only two of 30 trials using induction chemotherapy have shown a survival advantage, despite many showing impressive tumor response. In addition, several studies utilizing induction chemotherapy have demonstrated a decrease in the incidence of distant metastases.^{46,47} Phase II trials of induction chemotherapy have shown cisplatin and 5-fluorouracil to have a tumor response rates as high as 80%. Subset analysis from a large meta-analysis have shown a 5% improvement in survival with induction chemotherapy with cisplatin and 5-FU as compared to patients treated with surgery and/or RT alone. Response rates as high as 93% have been demonstrated with the addition of a taxane, such as docetaxel, to the cisplatin and 5-FU induction regimen, however, survival benefits remain to be documented. Unfortunately, acute toxicities including mucositis, and renal toxicity are increased with induction chemotherapy and may further increase the risk of these toxicities with subsequent CCRT.⁴⁹

Neoadjuvant chemotherapy, chemotherapy given prior to surgery, for SCCHN is not often used in the United States; however, European centres have shown some success with neoadjuvant chemotherapy for laryngeal carcinoma.⁵⁰ Neither induction nor neoadjuvant chemotherapy for SCCHN has a currently set standard population or regimen and should still be considered investigational.

I. Metastatic/Recurrent Disease

Cisplatin has been found to be the most active single agent in the treatment of SCCHN and has been shown to result in a 10 week's survival advantage over best supportive care in patients with locally and distantly recurrent disease or advanced disease not amenable to surgery or radiation therapy. Numerous multidrug regimens have been evaluated for the treatment of SCCHN. A phase III trial of platinum/5FU versus MTX showed a statistically significant improvement in complete and partial response with cisplatin/5-FU compared to methotrexate ($p < 0.001$) and improved response with carboplatin/5-FU versus methotrexate ($p = 0.05$). Unfortunately, the multidrug regimens, especially the cisplatin/5-FU arm, were associated with greater toxicity without an improvement in overall survival.

Re-irradiation is emerging as a treatment for recurrent disease or new second primary cancers with cure or palliation attainable in a significant percentage of patients. Several phase II studies combining re-irradiation with various chemotherapy regimens have reported 5-year overall survival rates ranging from 15–38%. Although the local control and survival rates are encouraging, both the acute and long-term toxicity of combined chemotherapy and re-irradiation are significant, with fatal complications observed in 10–20% of patients. Currently, studies are investigating biologic modifiers such bevacizumab and amifostine with re-irradiation in an attempt to reduce the acute and late toxicities of treatment.

J. Other Factors

Several factors affect the responsiveness of the disease to cytotoxic therapy: previous treatment, tumor burden, and the patient's performance status.⁸ Localized disease and good

performance status portend higher response.

Hypoxia is a factor which affects tumor cell sensitivity to radiotherapy because oxygen is required for radiation to cause cell death.⁸ Several radio-sensitizing agents have been evaluated for the treatment of SCCHN. To date the results have been disappointing as none have shown an improvement in survival.⁴²⁻⁴⁴ Tiripazimine, a radio-sensitizing agent that is reduced to its active form under hypoxic conditions, combined with cisplatin/RT is being evaluated in a currently enrolling phase III trial.

Other areas of investigation include dose intensification with altered radiation fractionation schedules with a goal to improve tumor control and/or decrease the probability of long-term treatment complications. Hyper-fractionation increases the number of daily radiation treatments while accelerated radiotherapy decreases the overall treatment time by giving higher daily doses. Patients treated with hyper-fractionation and accelerated fractionation with a concomitant boost achieved significant improvement in locoregional control with a trend towards improved disease free survival compared to standard fractionation; however, there were increased acute, but not late, treatment related toxicities. Several other randomized trials and multiple phase II trials have also shown improved tumor control with altered fractionation combined with concurrent chemotherapy versus radiation therapy alone. Again, many of these trials have shown increased toxicity with combined modality therapy over radiotherapy alone.

Rehabilitation

Post-treatment rehabilitation is vital in patients with oral cavity SCC because significant functional morbidity is encountered that affects speech, swallowing, and/or mastication. Oral rehabilitation commences at the time of initial consultation and is coordinated by a speech pathologist. Input from a dentist and prosthodontist, however, is also vital for successful and expedient rehabilitation in these patients.

Prognostic Factors & Outcome

The overall disease-specific survival rate for patients who have oral cavity SCC is approximately 50%.⁵ Patients with early-stage tumors (T1 or T2) have survival rates of 70% to 90%. Those with more advanced stage (ie, stage III or IV) of disease have survival rates of less than 25%. The addition of radiotherapy has significantly improved disease-specific outcome in these patients, however. The most important factor for prognosis is the state of the cervical lymphatics, with survival rates halved in the presence of pathologic nodal involvement.

Discussion

The past two decades have confirmed the role of chemotherapy in the treatment of SCCHN. There is sufficient evidence to employ CCRT for unresectable SCCHN and in the adjuvant setting, with the understanding that adjuvant CCRT should be limited to populations with poor prognostic factors. Adjuvant CCRT should not be considered standard of care for all patients post-resection.^{41,42} Induction chemotherapy can not be considered standard in the treatment of maxillary squamous cell carcinoma, while there is data demonstrating tumor response rates, survival benefit is not consistently documented. Increased intensity of therapy requires close communication between oncologists and knowledgeable

dental providers in order that appropriate dental preventive care is completed prior to cancer therapy.

It can be a disfiguring, slowly progressive disease leading to significant physical and emotional scars. The current goal of therapy is cure with a premium on preservation of organ function and, as data emerges, CCRT is becoming a standard modality in the treatment of SCCHN. These advances have increased the cure rates with a concomitant increase in toxicity; therefore, active research still needs to be pursued to ameliorate the toxicities associated with these therapies as more patients are cured of their disease.

As CCRT becomes more widely utilized, the morbidities associated with these therapies will become more common. This is certainly the case for oro-pharyngeal mucositis, which is more common (almost 100%) and more severe and of longer duration than in single modality treatment. Prevention and management of these toxicities are needed as oropharyngeal mucositis is a treatment limiting toxicity. Long term organ dysfunction including laryngeal function, dysphagia, taste, salivary gland dysfunction associated with CCRT need to be carefully studied, in order to improve current management.

As with treatment of many other malignancies, new molecularly directed chemotherapeutic agents are being studied as possible adjuncts or replacements for standard cytotoxic agents. The role of new directed agents, such as epidermal growth factor receptor modulators and farnesyl transferase inhibitors is still under investigation and will further defined as studies continue. They offer potential treatment with fewer side effects by localizing therapy to the tumor bed. In addition, agents such as capecitabine may offer a method of delivering chemotherapy to patients who, due to the significant side effects innate to standard agents, may not be candidates for conventional chemotherapy.

Recent advances in radiation therapy with intensity modulated radiation therapy (IMRT) has allowed shaping of the three-dimensional field of RT and varying beam intensity possible resulting in rapid dose gradients outside of the target and reducing dose to surrounding normal tissues. IMRT is ideally suited for head and neck malignancies given the proximity of these tumors to critical structures, including the brainstem, optic chiasm, and salivary glands. The use of IMRT for many head and neck carcinomas has been shown to result in comparable disease control as standard radiotherapy, while reducing acute and late toxicity. IMRT can significantly reduce radiation dose to the salivary glands, decreasing the long-term incidence of hyposalivation; thereby, leading to improved quality of life. The advances in IMRT require close communication between the oncologist, radiation oncologist, and dental provider in order that following RT, dental providers be aware of the sites of bone exposed to high dose fields, due to implications for dental treatment in the high dose volume.

Advances in management of advanced stage disease, and recurrent disease including CCRT and re-irradiation protocols carry the potential for cure but with an increased risk of toxicity. Concurrent and induction chemotherapy increase the severity of oral mucositis and may lead to renal toxicity and myelosuppression. Induction chemotherapy, current combined therapy and re-irradiation protocols are associated with increased duration and severity of ulcerative oral mucositis, and increased risk of local and systemic infection including

candidiasis. The severity of oral mucositis is a significant treatment limiting complication of therapy that may lead to the need for opioid analgesics, weight loss, dehydration, tube feeding, and interruption in or cessation of therapy. Tube feeding, systemic analgesics, antimicrobials and admission to hospital greatly increase the cost of care. Because of this, there is an increased need for effective prophylaxis of oral mucositis, and effective pain management. The impact of mucositis on patients and upon the ability to deliver cancer therapy has led to considerable research in potential prophylactic treatment of ulcerative mucositis. Pain management requires effective utilization of analgesic ladder for pain management including nonopioids, opioids, adjuvant medications and adjuvant psychological and physical therapies. Topical analgesics may be valuable for the pain of local mucosal damage.

Chronic toxicities including salivary gland hypofunction and oral/dental complications associated with hyposalivation that may affect all oral tissues and oral function including caries risk, periodontal disease, difficulty with dental function, reduced or altered taste, mucosal sensitivity, mucosal necrosis and osteonecrosis. The risk of tissue necrosis is elevated in patients with re-radiation with or without chemotherapy. Advances in therapy, including IMRT has been shown to lessen hyposalivation and increase the potential benefit of sialogogues to increase salivation by stimulation of non-irradiated glands. The development of targeted therapies provides the potential for improved cure with reduced toxicity. Until that time, prevention, early diagnosis and management of oral complications in maxillary squamous cell carcinoma patients is of increased importance, best managed by integrated teams of medical and dental providers.

Summary

Oral cavity SCC remains a significant health problem and requires a multidisciplinary approach. Treatment with surgery alone or in combination with adjuvant radiotherapy for more advanced lesions is the standard of care. Major advances have been made in surgical approaches, reconstructive options, and the rehabilitation of patients who have oral cavity SCC. These advances have significantly improved disease-specific outcome and quality of life. The future may lie in the development of treatment regimes that combine early detection with organ preservation and result in improved cure rates and quality of life.

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